

Competence Centre Charter

Lead Partner:	GARR
Version:	1.0
Status:	
Dissemination Level:	Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10048176
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.10048176

Deliverable Abstract

Skills4EOSC establishes a network of Competence Centres in Europe pivotal for driving Open Science. These hubs, tailored to specific regions or domains, offer crucial knowledge in Open Science practices and FAIR data management. They bridge gaps in expertise through training, linking stakeholders to national and international programs. These centres, diverse in structure and focus, serve as recognised point of reference, connecting various stakeholders and promoting standardized practices. Their success relies on engaging researchers, policy-makers, universities, and others, tailoring trainings to their needs.

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

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DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>	Sara Di Giorgio	GARR	01.12.22
<i>Moderated by:</i>	Emma Lazzeri	GARR	01.12.22
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	<i>Skills4EOSC Technical Board</i>		01.12.22
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	<i>Clara Lines</i>	DCC	07.02.23
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	<i>Arnaud Gingold</i>	OPERAS	07.02.23
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	<i>Luciano Gaido</i>	INFN	07.02.23
<i>Approved by:</i>	Emma Lazzeri	GARR	31.08.23

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
<i>v.0.1</i>	01.12.23	<i>Draft version shared with TB</i>	<i>S. Di Giorgio</i>
<i>v.0.2</i>	03.07.23	<i>Document review</i>	<i>C. Lines, A. Gingold, L. Gaido, O. Prnjat, C. Sharma, L. Berberi, L. Candela, L. Schirru, K. Avanco, I. Souyiultzoglou, Skills4EOSC Technical</i>

			<i>Board.</i>
<i>v.1.0</i>	31.08.23	<i>Document approved</i>	<i>E. Lazzeri</i>

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CC	Competence Centre
CCNet	Coordination Network of Competence Centres
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
MVSS	Minimum Viable Skillsets
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
S4E	Skills4EOSC
ToT	Training of Trainers

Contents

1	Executive summary	5
1.1	Introduction	5
1.2	Skills4EOSC Competence Centre definition	5
1.2.1	Skills4EOSC Competence Centre mission	6
1.2.2	Competence Centre target stakeholders	7
1.2.3	Characteristics and requirements	8
1.2.4	Skills4EOSC Competence Centre activities and services portfolio	9

1 Executive summary

1.1 Introduction

Skills4EOSC aims at building a **Coordination Network of Competence Centres across Europe (CCNet)**. The Skills4EOSC CCNet will be based on a lightweight mechanism to align and coordinate the network nodes.

Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Node (CC) represents a **point of reference** in a specific Country/Region/Domain to find key competencies to enable the practice of Open Science with adequate knowledge of standards, applications and tools and best practices for delivering, managing, re-using, sharing and analysing FAIR data, as well as other digital research objects. The nodes within the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network are accessible in a [Registry](#) presented within a section of the project's website.

The concept of Competence Centre is not new but it is already used in several contexts such as the High Performance Computing ([NCCs in HPC](#)), the Chips Act and Semiconductor field ([ALLPROS](#)), and the Conservation of Cultural Heritage ([4CH](#)). In other cases, such as [ENRIO](#), the reference points are not referred to as Competence Centres, yet they provide support services, training, and assistance.

1.2 Skills4EOSC Competence Centre definition

In the Skills4EOSC's vision, **Competence Centres (S4E CCs) are dedicated to knowledge organization and transfer in the Open Science**, FAIR research output management and EOSC context, in their countries, region or thematic domain. They address the skills shortage by offering to training, including workforce upskilling and reskilling on Open Science. They connect stakeholders to national and international programs linked to OS and EOSC and act as an access point to network on OS and FAIR research. They are usually associated with excellence, training and knowledge transfer, interdisciplinarity, standardization, and a collaborative approach of different institutions or departments. The structure, operational mode and

organization of Competence Centres may vary very widely depending on the Country, Region or Domain they operate in.

These entities must be centres recognised at national/regional or thematic level by the research community. They can either be established as national initiatives (as is the case of ICDI in Italy) or organisations which have the leading or mandated contribution to the OS activities nationally (such as a National cloud provider, National Research and Education Network, or a core university like TU-Delft and 4TUResearch.Data in The Netherlands). CCs could be also established on the domain level and supported by ESFRI Research infrastructures, such as OPERAS and EPOS.

1.2.1 Skills4EOSC Competence Centre mission

CC's mission is to provide a **shared hub of expertise in implementing Open Science** and FAIR data principles, offering leadership, training, coordination and cataloguing services to connect relevant people, guidance, learning resources and curricula.

CCs pool the expertise available within research institutions, universities and thematic and cross-discipline research infrastructures. They support interested stakeholders in adopting and developing OS policies and practices and offer training and support, empowerment, lifelong learning, professionalization and resources and services to a variety of stakeholders, including not only researchers and data stewards, but also funders, decision-makers, civil servants, and industry. CCs activity is based on awareness raising, promoting best practices and success stories.

Skills4EOSC provides each CC with a **program of Training of Trainers** – designed on the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVSs) defined by WP2 - targeting different profiles defined by the project (ranging from policymakers to data stewards, researchers to professionals and legal and ethical advisors) and on different topics or domains (eg: Ethical, Legal and Social Issues - ELSI -

aspects, RDM workflows in different disciplines, etc). For each ToT session, a Master Trainer will be identified in the CC Node and will attend the training.

So the competence set that each CC node needs to incorporate will be based on the MVSs delivered by WP2.

Moreover the Skills4EOSC CC has to adopt other key results such as the FAIR-by-design methodology for learning resources, the quality assurance and certification framework.

1.2.2 Competence Centre target stakeholders

Stakeholders play a critical role in the success of Skills4EOSC Competence Centres, each with their unique interests and contributions. Here's a list of these stakeholders and what drives their involvement:

- **Researchers:** Driven to enhance their skills and knowledge in Open Science.
- **Data support professionals, such as Data Stewards:** Eager to expand their expertise within the Open Science domain.
- **Decision and policymakers:** Involved in shaping policies and regulations to advance Open Science.
- **Governmental organizations and Ministries:** Committed to providing support and oversight for Open Science initiatives at the national level.
- **University networks:** Focused on developing competencies to promote Open Science within academic institutions.
- **Funding organizations:** Dedicated to channelling resources into open and FAIR research projects.
- **Legal and ethical advisors:** Committed to ensuring compliance with legal and ethical standards in Open Science endeavours.
- **Research Performing Organisations (RPOs):** Engaged in advancing Open Science practices within their organizations.
- **Discipline-specific research communities:** Contributing their expertise and knowledge to Open Science efforts.
- **Publishers and communicators:** Involved in disseminating research outputs and promoting Open Science publishing.

- **Honest brokers:** Facilitating the exchange of data and information in an impartial and trustworthy manner within the Open Science community.
- **EOSC actors and practitioners in the research lifecycle involved in Open Science:** Actively participating in various stages of the research process to promote openness and fairness.
- **Citizen scientists:** Enthusiastic volunteers who actively participate in scientific research.

1.2.3 Characteristics and requirements

To be eligible for inclusion within the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres network and registry a Competence Centre must meet the following mandatory requirements

1. **Demonstrated Commitment to Open Science and FAIR Principles:** The Competence Centre must showcase a proven dedication to the promotion and adoption of the Open Science framework and/or the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles at the regional, national, or domain-specific level. This commitment should be reflected in their active initiatives and advocacy efforts.
2. **Commitment to adoption of Skills4EOSC project outcomes:** To be eligible for inclusion within the Skills4EOSC network and registry, a Competence Centre must demonstrate a firm commitment to adopting the results of the Skills4EOSC project. This commitment involves adapting these outcomes as necessary to meet the specific needs of its community and actively participating in their continual development and evolution over time, making them available for the benefit of the broader network.
3. **Domain Authority:** The Competence Centre should possess the authority or recognized expertise within its designated domain of responsibility. This authority should also extend to Master Trainers who have actively participated in and successfully completed Skills4EOSC training courses, demonstrating their proficiency in Open Science and FAIR data management principles.
4. **Expertise Network:** The Centre must assemble a proficient group of Master Trainers encompassing various profiles and professionals

associated with Open Science and FAIR data management. This network should encompass a diverse range of skills and knowledge to effectively address the needs of the community.

5. **Engagement with target groups:** The Centre should actively engage with the identified target groups, understanding their specific requirements, and tailoring their services to meet those needs. This engagement is essential for effective knowledge dissemination and support.
6. **Training and Support:** The Centre should provide training services in various formats to a specific target group. These training offerings should encompass a broad spectrum of Open Science and FAIR data management topics. Additionally, the Centre should support its users by providing advice on the topics covered.
7. **Effective communication and knowledge dissemination:** The Competence Centre should communicate its activities and disseminate knowledge actively. This includes sharing information about its initiatives, best practices, and advancements in the field to a broader audience. The Centre should actively participate in the sharing of best practices, fostering collaboration and learning within the Skills4EOSC network. This involves contributing its expertise and insights to the broader community to enhance the collective knowledge and capabilities.

1.2.4 Skills4EOSC Competence Centre activities and services portfolio

In their endeavour to provide a portfolio of activities and services, Skills4EOSC Competence Centres (CCs) aim to offer a minimal viable set of initiatives tailored to meet the unique needs of their communities. This approach not only ensures the adoption of common practices but also promotes collaboration and encourages resource sharing across the boundaries of each CC. The following are key activities and services that CCs should consider including in their portfolio:

1. **Training-of-Trainers Courses:** CCs should develop and execute Training-of-Trainers courses, leveraging and potentially adapting the learning

materials provided by Skills4EOSC. This initiative is aimed at preparing a cadre of educators who can effectively train and upskill individuals in Open Science practices and FAIR data management.

2. **Plan and deliver community-specific training events:** Each CC should plan and execute a minimum of X training events each year, tailored to the specific needs and requirements of their target community. These events should provide practical knowledge and skills related to Open Science and FAIR principles.
3. **Collect user feedback and needs assessment:** CCs are responsible for actively collecting feedback from their community and identifying user needs related to Open Science and FAIR research. This feedback should be shared within the CCs Network to foster collaboration and the development of tailored solutions.
4. **Propose Minimum Viable Skillsets:** CCs are encouraged to propose the Minimum Viable Skillsets required for new career profiles in the field of Open Science, aligning them with the Skills4EOSC template and methodology. This ensures that emerging professionals possess the necessary competencies to drive Open Science forward.
5. **Adopt and maintain Skills4EOSC methodology:** CCs should adopt and consistently maintain the Skills4EOSC methodology, which serves as a standardized framework for Open Science education. Additionally, they should establish a Quality Assurance process for Open Science learning materials to ensure their relevance and effectiveness.
6. **Maintain active web presence and network interaction:** CCs are required to maintain up-to-date contact information and an active web presence, enabling seamless interaction with research institutions, other CCs within the Skills4EOSC network, and the EOSC Stakeholder Board. This fosters collaboration and information exchange.
7. **(TBD) Offer (IT) Services:** While not mandatory, CCs may consider offering IT services to their community. These services could include tools, technologies, or other resources that facilitate Open Science practices. The specific services offered can be determined based on the needs and capabilities of each CC.

Title of the Document

This holistic portfolio of activities and services equips Skills4EOSC Competence Centres with the tools and capabilities necessary to effectively promote and implement Open Science and FAIR data management practices within their respective communities, fostering common approaches, cooperation, and knowledge exchange across CC boundaries.